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Direct Infusion Workflow	1
Overall study design	1
Lipid extraction	1
Analytical platform	1
Quality control	1
Method qualification and validation	2
Reporting	2
Sample Descriptions	2
Primary podocyte control group and clock knockdown group / Mouse / Cells	2
Lipid Class Descriptions	2
1) FA[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid identification	2
1) FA[M-H] ⁻ / Lipid quantification	2

Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Detection of lipid metabolism after siRNA knockdown of Clock in primary podocytes			
Document creation date		05/27/2026		Principal investigator		jiang lei	
Institution		The Second Affiliated Hospital of Nanjing Medical University		Corresponding Email		wanghaiyan0124@163.com	
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted		Clinical		No	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		1-phase system		pH adjustment		None	
1-phase system		Isopropanol		Were internal standards added prior extraction?		Yes	

Analytical platform

Ionization additives		Ammonium formate, Formic acid		Detector		Mass spectrometer	
MS type		QQQ		MS vendor		Waters	
Direct type		Syringe		MS Level		MS ¹ , MS ²	
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹		Low resolution		Resolution at MS ¹		Unit	
Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹		Centroid mode		Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)		0.1	
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²		Low resolution		Resolution at MS ²		Unit	
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²		Centroid mode		Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used		No	

Quality control

Blanks		Yes		Type of Blanks		Extraction blank	
Quality control		Yes		Type of QC sample		Sample pool	

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	No
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request		

Sample Descriptions

Primary podocyte control group and clock knockdown group / Mouse / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles, Preservation method
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	between 10 and 15 minutes	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	0	Additives	None

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²		
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-		
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-		
Fragments for identification	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral loss of CO₂</td> </tr> </table>			Fragment name	Neutral loss of CO ₂
Fragment name					
Neutral loss of CO ₂					
Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	No		
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	No		
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No		
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	None		
Data manipulation	Smoothing	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No		
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A				

1) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s)	MS ²		

Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass
PG(d7)		

Internal lipid standard(s) MS¹

Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
PG(d7)	

Type of quantification	Calibration line	Type of calibration line	Solvent based
Response correction	No	Type I isotope correction	No
Limit of quantification	S/N ratio > 10	Normalization to reference	No
Lipid Quantification Software	None	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Further quantification remarks	None		